

Representation of Man and Woman in the Selected Novels of Sidhwa and Singh: A Corpus Stylistic Analysis

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Abstract

The present study is a comparative stylistic analysis of two novels *Train to Pakistan* and *The Ice Candy Man* by Khuswant Singh (1956) and Bapsi Sidhwa (1988) respectively. The purpose of this study is to explore the depiction of Man and Woman in the selected texts to find out the similarities and differences through which these characters are represented. The study utilizes a mixed method approach which combines both qualitative and quantitative methods. The focus of the research is the analysis of adjectives that have been used with Man and Woman in both the texts. For this purpose, the study utilizes corpus linguistic tool AntConc (3.2.1) to carry out a stylistic analysis of the texts. A total number of 56 adjectives with a total frequency of 107 times were analyzed. The study has found that women are underrepresented in the selected texts as more adjectives are used to represent men. Moreover, both the male and female writers, mostly, portray men positively while women are portrayed negatively. It is expected that this study will open new doors for future researchers and teachers to explore and understand the language of literature from new perspectives.

Keywords: adjectives, corpus stylistics, gender, man, Sidhwa, Singh, woman

1. Introduction

Stylistics is concerned with linguistic analysis of literary text. It analyzes a text from a linguistic point of view. Crystal (1972) defines stylistics as the systematic, situationally distinctive, intra-language variation. Thornborrow and Wareing (1998) defined Stylistics as "The study of style" (p. 2). There can be different stylistic approaches as the style can be of different forms which can be analyzed from different angles. The present study does not follow the traditional style of doing stylistic analysis but it carries out a Corpus based stylistic analysis. This approach lends reliability to the research. Corpus refers to "any collection of more than one text" (Wilson, 2001, p. 29). In other words, corpus is a body of text that is in electronic form and that can be run in a corpus software tool.

Corpus stylistics has gained much popularity in the study of literary texts because it helps the researchers to prove their point and elucidate their findings on the basis of concrete evidence. Different researchers like Starcke (2006), Stubbs (2005), and Murphy (2007) have utilized this approach to carry out their relevant research. The Pakistani and Indian English literature has been studied from various dimensions but there is still a dearth of corpus-based research in this area. The present research is an attempt to integrate stylistics and corpus linguistics to explore the selected texts to find out how male and female writers represent Man and Woman in their texts through a use of adjectives with a focus on the concrete evidence.

The novels selected for the present study are historical novels. But these represent men and women characters in their respective historical periods as well. The first novel selected for the study is *Train to Pakistan* (1956) written by Khushwant Singh, an Indian English writer. Though it is a story of religious persecution and the aftermath of the Partition of India in 1947, Singh (1956) has given a patriarchal representation of the women. Nooran, Haseena and Juggut's mother are some of the major female characters in the novel. Nooran is presented as unfaithful to her father because of having an illicit relationship with a dacoit. Haseena, a sixteen-year-old prostitute, serves an old man to get money. Juggut's mother is shown to be a woman who has to endure her son's disrespect and humiliations.

The second novel selected for the study is *The Ice Candy Man* written by a Pakistani female English writer, Bapsi Sidhwa (1988). The novel throws light on the political and social upheaval engendered by independence and Partition of India in 1947. While dealing with the problem of communal riots in the wake of Partition in this novel, Sidhwa (1988) represents a number of men and women characters. Lenny, the child narrator, suffers from Polio and records her observations about her surroundings in a detached manner. She observes and narrates the social changes around her. Lenny's mother, Mrs. Sethi and other Parsi women help Hindu and Sikh families and women to move to safer places. Lenny's Godmother rescues the Hindu Ayah who had been forcibly married to her Muslim friend, the seller of ice-candies. The researcher is interested to explore following question through a corpus-based analysis of both these selected novels: How are the man and woman represented through a use of adjectives in the selected works of Sidhwa and Singh?

2. Literature Review

The genre of fiction highlights certain issues through a reflection of the socio-economic and socio-psychological happenings across the societies of different ages. Post-colonial fiction especially that of India and Pakistan is important not only for projecting the partition scenario but it carries different ideologies. This partition of the sub-continent carried with it a number of societal and psychological devastations as claimed by different post-colonial writers. According to Hassan (1997), the continuing effect of partition on the affected people is even worse than the bloodshed that occurred at that particular time. Many post-colonial writers have captured and portrayed this trauma left by partition in both English and Urdu novels. With a central focus on the theme of partition the novels highlighted the related pains and pangs of human history i.e. the riots, disturbances, treachery, robbing, killing, abduction and rape of the women. These related

themes have been portrayed by different writers differently based upon their own differing faiths, experiences, ideologies and understandings.

A number of studies have been carried out to analyze these partition related themes. But this depiction of partition time as enclosed in these post-colonial novels was also studied from a gender perspective. Dey (2018) claims that it would be untrue to claim that women are entirely absent from Partition history. Hence, a number of studies are carried out to see the plight of women during this time period. For example, Dey (2018) has analyzed the partition of India in relation to its effect on female body and male violence as depicted in Sidhwa's (1988) *Ice Candy Man*. Another analysis of the same novel has been carried out by Shahnawaz (2022) in order to explore the physical and social exploitation of women. Ali et al. (2020) have analyzed the use of only one lexical item i.e. adjectives in Sidhwa's work. Their study has highlighted the miserable and weak position of women in a typical patriarchal society. Another study with a focus on the study of adjectives in relation to depiction of female character was carried out by Rashid et al. (2020). In their exploration of Ibsen's *A Doll's House*, they have found that Norwegian women are depicted as dependent, stupid submissive and fragile. Nehere and Bhabad (2014) have studied these consequences and sufferings of partition portrayed in *Train to Pakistan* with special reference to female characters that how they were dragged, killed and raped at that time of partition. Their study has highlighted the subjugated position of the women who were considered as things to be used for insult and revenge.

The present work is different from the previous studies because it does not focus on postcolonial themes or is not limited to the study of only female characters. But it aims at analyzing the depiction of man and woman through a use of adjectives in the selected postcolonial works. Moreover, the present study is corpus-based study.

The works selected for the present study are '*Ice Candy Man*' and '*Train to Pakistan*' written by Sidhwa (1988) and Singh (1956) respectively. Sidhwa (1988) in '*The Ice Candy Man*' depicts how the harmonious and peaceful life of the people belonging to different religions and societies was disturbed due to partition. She describes in an appealing way through her child narrator, Lenny, how these people living in peace and harmony turned against each other which resulted in many societal and psychological damages. This depiction of violence in *The Ice-Candy-Man* carries within it the oppression and victimization of women characters. The major female voices in this novel are those of Shanta-the Ayah, Lenny, her mother and her grandmother. Likewise, Singh (1956) in his *Train to Pakistan* apparently portrays the partition situation and its related havoc to highlight his theme that this partition was an illogical historical act resulting in the suffering and division of humans of this region. Other than this major theme of partition, Singh's attitude and representation of women in this novel is noteworthy. Purohit (2012) has claimed that women in Singh's novel are shown to be passive, victimized, oppressed and engaged in their daily domestic routines. With an apparent and major theme of partition, the present study utilizes these two novels as a text to find out the differences in the depiction of man and woman by a female and male writer. For this purpose, the study utilizes stylistic analysis.

According to Simpson (2003), language is given the main point of stylistic analysis in textual interpretation. Stylistics involves the analysis of meaning and carries out literary criticism through a focus on certain stylistic features occurring in sequence. This process in stylistic analysis helps in grasping the hidden meanings in a text. Stylistics is the study of literary discourse from a linguistic point of view (Widdowson, 2014). Hence, Stylistics is the study of language and its hidden meaning through identification of any marked feature of a language i.e. stylistic feature. Li (2009) has elaborated these stylistic features by dividing these into linguistic, textual and contextual features. Stylisticians try to maintain and explain why certain choices are made by the writers in their texts while using language. A stylistics study is the use of language in specific contexts and attempts to account for the characteristics that mark the language use of individuals and social groups (Wright, 2000). This idea of style resting upon the choice of the author to express his ideas using certain linguistic patterns is further substantiated by McEnery and Wilson (1996). They even claim that this choice by the writer must be measurable to some degree.

From within two approaches of stylistic analysis, the present study utilizes a corpus-based approach. Corpus based means electronic analysis of a given text for the identification and understanding of language used. Stylistics, the linguistic analysis of a text, when combined with corpus linguistics results in corpus stylistics. Wynne and Prytz (2005) have claimed that such a study is opening up new vistas for the analysis of literary language. A corpus -based approach adopted to study language is more empirical and strengthened with evidence from the data. Moreover, Biber (2011) has pointed out that such an analysis carries reliability and widens the scope.

3. Methodology

What makes this research a mixed method research is the use of both qualitative and quantitative methodologies of research. This corpus-based study is also a comparative study because it compares two corpora to find out the similarities and differences in the usage of adjectives with Man and Woman. In order to compile the corpus, the selected novels were downloaded from the internet and converted into word files. This word file was then converted into two separate text files i.e. TTP and TICM which stand for *Train to Pakistan* (1956) and *The Ice Candy Man* respectively.

3.1 Data Analysis

AntConc corpus analysis toolkit was utilized to collect and analyze the data. AntConc (3.2.1) offers different options like Concordance, Concordance plot, File view, Clusters, Collocates, Wordlist, and Keyword list. For the present study, Clusters and Concordance options were used to collect and analyze adjectives used with man and woman. Firstly, the clusters program was utilized to search the data for all the instances of adjectives. The data were searched for two search terms 'woman' and 'man' where the search term position was set 'on Right'. The cluster size was set at 2 and the minimum cluster frequency was set at 1 to collect all the occurrences of adjectives with the search terms. This search provided the researchers with all the cluster types for the searched terms (see Appendix A for screenshots). Out of these cluster types, the researchers kept only those cluster types for analysis which showed a pattern of Adjective + man and adjective + woman (see Appendix B for data in tabular form). After collecting the relevant data and organizing it in tabular forms, the concordances option of AntConc (3.2.1) was utilized. Each pattern was explored in this program and the concordance pattern for each was utilized to discuss the context of each adjective. These identified adjectives are presented in the findings and discussion section in the form of graphs followed by a detailed discussion. This discussion is also supported with the help of instances from the text where needed to highlight the themes and ideas propagated by the respective writers.

4. Findings and Discussion

After presenting the lists of adjectives used with man and woman in tabular form (see Appendix), this section discusses the variation which occurs in both the corpus related to the projection of both in each.

4.1 Adjectives related to Man in TTP

A search for adjectives used with 'man' in TTP ends with an identification of total, resulting in identification of total 19 adjectives used with man (see Table 1, Appendix B). Figure 1 given below shows that the most frequently used adjective for man in TTP is 'young' with a frequency of 13. The adjective 'old' is the second most frequent adjective with a frequency of 6, followed by 'educated' and 'lean' with a frequency of 2 each. All the other adjectives appear only once with the term 'man' in TTP.

Figure 1: Adjectives for man in TTP

It is important to note the usage of these adjectives in context. Out of these 19 adjectives as given in figure 1, 13 adjectives are used with positive connotation while only 6 are used with negative connotation. The adjectives used to portray man positively are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Adjectives for Man in TTP with positive connotation

The adjectives used in TTP with man carrying positive meanings are meant to idealize the man as a young, educated, big brave, great, religious, tall and wise man. All these traits highlight the man as a superior creature. The strength of the man is highlighted when he is called as big and brave. His positive personality is also shown through portraying him an educated and religious person.

The representation of man as an ideal character is also supported by the study of concordance lines. The theme that men are brave is focused in the following examples taken from TTP:

The man stretched himself on the rope.[...]. He was a **big man**.
The man hacked the rope vigorously.
A man started climbing on the steel span
 He is the **tallest man** in this area

Another theme projected by Singh (1956) is that men are brave and wise. For example:

Sardar Juggut Singh, we agree you are a **big brave man**
 You have the district's **bravest man** to look after you
 You are a **clever man**,
 He is a **great man**

The man is shown to be experienced as in 'The head constable was a **man** of experience'. Moreover, the superiority of man over woman is also reflected through a choice of words when the researchers searched concordance lines for the term man as in:

the man in front, the girl a few paces behind him.

Other than these themes, the text also presents man characters who are educated religious and well mannered.

But Meet Singh was a **man** of peace.
 Juggut Singh is not a **man** of hollow words
 You as an educated **man** know what would happen
 All the world respects a **religious man**. Look at Gandhi!
 The sub-inspector, who was a **younger man**, had a more sophisticated manner

Other than this positive representation of man through positive use of adjectives, the data has given the examples where man is portrayed negatively as well. However, it is important to note that negative adjectives are used less and with less frequency as compared to the adjectives used in positive connotation with man (see Table 3, see Appendix2). The adjectives like old, lean, clever, lifeless, small, tired and violent are used which point out the dark side of a man's personality. Figure 3 below presents these adjectives along with the frequency:

Figure 3: Adjectives for Man in TTP with negative connotation

The representation of man through negative traits is also supported by the study of concordance lines. This representation as a weak, absent minded and disappointed and old creature can be noticed in examples from TTP given below:

Reference to the police awakened the **old man** from his absent-minded listening.
 The **old man** gave a wry smile.
 The **old man** hobbled out of the courtyard
 The **man** shivered and collapsed

Other than through these characteristics associated with old age, the man is portrayed though with less frequency as a lean and tired man which refers to his physical weakness:

He was a tall **lean man** with a clipped beard.
 He was a tall, **lean man**,
 Hukum Chand looked a **tired man**

The bad character of man is also highlighted in the corpus as in 'he was officially declared a man of bad character.' On the basis of findings discussed above it is found that Singh (1956) in his novel Train to Pakistan has presented the man mostly positively. It is found that 68% adjectives are used to present man positively while only 32 % are used with negative connotation. The man is presented as an embodiment of strength, bravery, wisdom, knowledge, experience and greatness. And this is proved by the study of selective adjectives supported by a number of concordance lines.

4.2 Adjectives related to Man in TICM

The search for clusters related to adjective + man in TICM has given 22 examples which are greater than those appeared in TTP corpus. But their frequency and nature show a different approach to represent man. Man is not portrayed through extraordinarily positive traits. And the frequency with which these appear in TICM (see Table 4, appendix 2) is also less as compared to TTP corpus.

Figure 4 presents these identified adjectives in TICM with a frequency of each. 'Ice-candy' is the most frequently used adjective with a frequency of 6. The adjective 'old' is the second most frequent adjective with a frequency of 4, followed by 'holy' and 'grown' with a frequency of 3 and 2 respectively.

Figure 4: Adjectives for man in TICM

The data reveals eleven examples where man is shown positively in TICM through a use of adjectives related to his profession, age, size and other personality traits. The projection of the man does not portray him as an extraordinary creature. Sidhwa (1988) appears not to be partial towards the portrayal of man in her work. She has treated man in a normal way through the use of adjectives. The most frequent cluster appearing in the corpus is 'Ice Candy man' which refers to the profession of the man only and does not highlight his superiority. The term medicine man again refers to his profession while mountain man refers to the area to which a man belonged to. Even the use of the adjective as large man, refers to his large body structure. The other traits through which man is presented are holy, dear, fair, good, gentle and younger man. Figure 5 displays the frequencies with which these adjectives appear in TICM.

Figure 5: Adjectives for man in TICM with positive connotation

The co-text and context of these adjectives when studied through concordance lines has given following instances which present man positively.

So they sack Wavell Sahib, a **fair man**
 He has become a **black-faced gentle-man**
 He is a **large man**, as big-bellied and broad-beamed as Imam Din
 a young, **good-looking man**.
Ice-candy-man, gleaning wisdom from his comments on life

It is noteworthy that Sidhwa (1988) has presented man equally as positive and negative. The corpus has given 50 % examples where man is represented negatively through a use of adjectives like old, grown, aged, bad, poor, thin etc (see table 6, appendix B). Figure 6 below shows these adjectives with their frequency as well.

Figure 6: Adjectives for man in TICM with negative connotation

A study of concordance lines also shows how Sidhwa (1988) has presented the man through his bad nature and bad qualities. The old age is projected as an impotent age where man cannot harm others.

Aren't you ashamed of burning and maiming a harmless **old man** like me?

Other lines where man is painted through dark color are given below.

He is a **paunchy man**
 He is a dark, **middle-aged man**
 Her husband is not a **bad man**.
 He is a short, **chubby man**, with a totally bald and brown head.
 Tota Ram was an important, frightening and **grown man**.
 You are not a **man**, you are a low-born, two-bit evil little mouse
 He is not a **man** for preliminary niceties.
Ice candy-man, lean as his popsicles
Ice-candy-man is visibly shaken.[...] Treacherous, dangerous, contemptible.

All these examples from the text show that Sidhwa (1988) has projected the man through a number of negative traits.

4.3 Adjectives related to Woman in TTP

The representation of woman through adjectives is quite less in TTP when it is compared to the frequency of adjectives occurring with man in TTP. There are a total number of 20 adjectives used to represent man but only 5 examples are noted for woman. The analysis of adjectives with woman and the study of concordance lines show that woman is mostly projected as an old, weak and victimized creature in the selected text. Table 7 presents a list of adjectives appearing with woman in TTP.

Figure 7: Adjectives occurring with woman in TTP

The adjectives given in Table 7 shows that woman is totally portrayed as a negative character possessing not a single positive quality in her. The term old woman appears in the text to present woman as a weak, suppressed and emotional creature. Concordance lines as cited below prove this point:

implored the **older woman**.
 pleaded the **old woman**.
 The **old woman** stopped moaning.
 It the **old woman** and the girl prostitute.
 the **old woman** asked angrily.
 the **old woman** hissed.
A woman wailed.

Another theme that the text brings into light is that woman is like a commodity to be used and abducted.

to buy an **abducted woman**.
 For each **woman** they abduct or rape, abduct two.
 One should never touch another's property; one should never look at **another's woman**.

The woman is also presented as a coward and weak creature when there is a reference to the henna and bangles of a woman. As in Malli is not a **woman** with henna on his palms or bangles on his wrists. The woman is further relegated to negative position through her ugly physical appearance as in the old **toothless woman** broke into a sonorous singsong of praise.

Hence, it can be observed that Sindh in his Train to Pakistan has portrayed women negatively through a number of adjectives as compared to the positive representation of the man.

4.4 Adjectives related to Woman in TICM

The list of adjectives appearing with woman in TICM is greater than that in TTP. Like TTP, in TICM all the adjectives carry negative connotations with them but the analyses of concordance lines show some difference in the attitude of both the writers. Singh (1956) has presented woman negatively in most of the cases but Sidhwa (1988) here and there highlights her positive traits as well but this picture is quite contrary to that of the representation of the man.

Figure 8: Adjectives for woman in TICM

The adjectives used with woman as shown in Table 8 project the woman as a negative creature where she is shown to be suppressed and sorrowful. In Fallen woman, the adjective fallen refers to woman who has been kidnapped and raped and as result she is not accepted by her family. As Lenny asks Hamida, Are you a **fallen woman**? And text narrates later what does it mean when grandmother tells Lenny that Hamida was **kidnapped** by the Sikhs, [...] the husband, or his family won't take her back. The other adjectives like poor, fate-smitten, sorrowing and wailing further relegate the woman to a position of inferiority where she is always suffering the hardships of life. Another theme brought into light is the desire of the society for male children where a son-less woman is projected with a desire for having a son. Other than these adjectives with negative connotation, some concordance lines are noted which support the same negative picture of the woman in the text.

The woman [...] awkward and uncomfortably tall [...] Her eyes are downcast and a nervous,
The woman in the jail has stopped wailing
 A **middle-aged woman** without a veil, her hair dishevelled,
 To you, **this son-less woman** is queen
 This **poor woman** wants a son! She has four daughters
 and that **hooting, rollicking woman** my remote and solemn mother?

Poor fate-smitten woman

What can a **sorrowing woman** do but wail?

soothe the **wailing woman**

Oye, **mad woman**, hisses Father through the door,

Other than this negative state of affairs, women are also presented in traditional roles. The duty of a woman is to work at home and serve the family. Same theme is highlighted when a woman offers herself for a job in following words:

[...] says **the woman** in thickly accented, village Punjabi. "I will sweep, clean, milk the buffalo, churn the butter [...] After all, I have been a housewife

Another stereotype attached to woman is her beautiful seductive nature. The text also presents the desaiuracle beauty of a woman as Lenny sees Ayyah and narrates as:

the **flashy woman** with the blazing lipstick and chalky powder and a huge pink

hibiscus in her hair,

The adjectives given in table above and the discussed concordance lines explicitly point out how Sidhwa (1988) has represented the traditional beliefs about woman i.e. a woman is to stay at home, provide pleasure to man and has to live a miserable life as a sorrowful creature.

5. Conclusion

This corpus –based comparative study of two selective texts has tried to find out how man and woman are represented through a use of adjective. This novel research has used corpus stylistics to collect the required data for analysis. The lists of adjectives retrieved through the cluster program of Antconc (3.2.1) and a thorough reading of concordance lines relevant to man and woman have revealed some interesting findings. On the basis of the findings and analysis, it can be concluded that a total number of 56 adjectives from both the corpora were collected to carry out the study. Out of these 56 adjectives, 41 adjectives are identified to be used for men and only 15 adjectives are used for women. On the basis of this, the study claims that women are underrepresented while men are given more descriptions. The corpus wise detailed division of these adjectives for man and woman is given in Figure 9.

The study has found a difference in the treatment of the representation of man and woman by selected two writers. There are more descriptions of man in Singh's (1956) *Train to Pakistan* as compared to the description of woman. A total number of 19 adjectives are used to describe man while only 5 adjectives are used to describe woman in his novel (see Figure 9). The male is mostly projected through the adjectives with positive connotation (68%) while (32%) adjectives are used to represent them negatively. In comparison to this all the adjectives used to describe women are carrying negative connotations. There is not a single example of the use of adjective with woman that portrays her with positive colors. In contrast to this unequal representation of man and woman through adjectives, Sidhwa (1988), the female writer gives a balanced picture of both the genders. She too has used more adjectives (22) to represent men as compared to those for women (10). But she has described man both positively (50%) and negatively (50%). She has not provided a highly idealized picture of the man. On the contrary she too has represented women through all the adjectives with negative connotations (see figure 9).

Figure 9: Adjectives used positively/negatively for man and woman in TTP and TICM

Figure 9 clearly shows that TTP uses 19 adjectives for man and 5 for woman (total 24) while TICM uses 22 adjectives for man and 10 for woman (total 32). Hence, the study concludes that Sidhwa in her TICM uses more adjectives as compared to that of Singh in his TTP.

Other than this division of adjectives occurring in both the corpora, the frequency with which these adjectives appear in the text is also important to note (see Figure 10). The total number of adjectives was 56 but the frequency with which these adjectives appear in the corpus is 107. The division of the frequency of these adjectives' corpus-wise and gender-wise is given in detail in Table 9 (see appendix B). Frequency wise, TTP shows a greater number of the usage of adjectives i.e. 61 while TICM makes a use of adjectives for 46 times only. Singh (1956), the male writer, in TTP has presented the idealized picture of the man where he presents man more positively through positive adjectives (26 adjectives) while he presents man through negative adjectives for only 12 times. But the adjectives he uses for women are all to show her negative side (23 adjectives). Likewise, Sidhwa has also presented man positively (18 adjectives) and negatively (15 adjectives) both but all the 13 adjectives that she uses for women put the women in a weaker position. On the basis of frequency, it is concluded that Singh (1956) in his TTP uses adjectives more frequently as compared to Sidhwa (1988) in her TICM.

Figure 10: Frequency of Adjectives used positively/negatively for man and woman in TTP and TICM

It can be concluded firstly, that women are underrepresented in the selected texts while men are given more descriptions through the use of adjectives. Out of selected 56 adjectives, 41 adjectives (73%) are used for men while only 15 adjectives (27%) are used for women. Irrespective of being male or female, both the writers use more adjectives for man as compared to those for the women. Singh, the male writer, use 19 adjectives for men while he uses only 5 for women. Sidhwa, the female writer, on the other hand, uses 22 adjectives for men while 10 for women. The second conclusion is related to the attitude of the writers in relation to the meaning and frequency with which each adjective appears with these opposing genders. Men with an exception of some negative traits are mostly portrayed to be young, brave, wise, experienced, educated, religious, and well-mannered. Women on the other hand are given no positive attributes. But they are portrayed as old, abducted, strange, fallen, poor, old, aged, sorrowful and wailing creatures. These findings of the study show the biased attitude of the writers towards the representation of women in texts. Moreover, the present research endeavored to explore the relationship between language, literature and corpus methodology. It has also proved that how the study of only one lexical item may be helpful to carry out a detailed and in-depth analysis of a literary text. It is expected that this study will support the authenticity and usability of corpus stylistic in the analysis of a literary text.

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Appendices

Appendix A

1. Representation of Man in TTP

Rank	Freq	Cluster
1	13	young man
2	12	The man
3	9	a man
4	9	old man
5	4	the man
6	3	one man
7	2	is man
8	2	another man
9	2	educated man
10	2	learn man
11	2	same man
12	1	big man
13	1	heavy man
14	1	bearest man
15	1	real man
16	1	clever man
17	1	fifth man
18	1	for man
19	1	great man
20	1	greatest man
21	1	he-man
22	1	lifeless man
23	1	married man
24	1	of man
25	1	one man
26	1	politeness. Man
27	1	religious man
28	1	rich man
29	1	small man
30	1	tallest man
31	1	this man
32	1	the man
33	1	tired man
34	1	villains man
35	1	wise man
36	1	younger man

Rank	Freq	Cluster
11	2	same man
12	1	big man
13	1	heavy man
14	1	bearest man
15	1	real man
16	1	clever man
17	1	fifth man
18	1	for man
19	1	great man
20	1	greatest man
21	1	he-man
22	1	lifeless man
23	1	married man
24	1	of man
25	1	one man
26	1	politeness. Man
27	1	religious man
28	1	rich man
29	1	small man
30	1	tallest man
31	1	this man
32	1	the man
33	1	tired man
34	1	villains man
35	1	wise man
36	1	younger man

2. Representation of Woman in TTP

Rank	Freq	Cluster
1	13	old woman
2	2	the woman
3	1	a woman
4	1	A woman
5	1	abducted woman
6	1	each woman
7	1	for woman
8	1	man, woman
9	1	other woman
10	1	is woman
11	1	strange woman
12	1	The woman
13	1	youngest woman

3. Representation of man in TICM

The first screenshot shows the results of a TICM analysis for the word 'man'. The top 25 clusters are listed below:

Rank	Freq	Cluster
1	140	candy-man
2	10	a man
3	9	the man
4	6	lowcastly-man
5	6	The man
6	4	old man
7	3	bearded man
8	3	hairy-man
9	2	grove man
10	2	no man
11	2	of man
12	2	populist man
13	2	populist-man
14	2	this man
15	1	A man
16	1	aged man
17	1	step man
18	1	bad man
19	1	behave man
20	1	shabby man
21	1	dead man
22	1	dear man
23	1	donkey-man
24	1	English-man
25	1	fair man

The second screenshot shows clusters 19 through 43:

Rank	Freq	Cluster
19	2	bad man
20	1	behave man
21	1	shabby man
22	1	dead man
23	1	dear man
24	1	donkey-man
25	1	English-man
26	1	fair man
27	1	flower-man
28	1	good man
29	1	horrid man
30	1	job man
31	1	large man
32	1	last man
33	1	looking man
34	1	medicine-man
35	1	mountain man
36	1	new man
37	1	paunchy man
38	1	poor man
39	1	stareman
40	1	then, man
41	1	this man
42	1	two-man
43	1	younger man

4. Representation of woman in TICM

The screenshot shows the results of a TICM analysis for the word 'woman'. The top 23 clusters are listed below:

Rank	Freq	Cluster
1	8	The woman
2	6	A woman
3	4	a woman
4	3	fallen woman
5	2	old woman
6	2	the woman
7	1	aged woman
8	1	American woman
9	1	Franky woman
10	1	Hindu woman
11	1	Indian woman
12	1	is woman
13	1	less woman
14	1	new woman
15	1	off, woman
16	1	poor woman
17	1	rolling woman
18	1	written woman
19	1	some woman
20	1	evening woman
21	1	that woman
22	1	wailing woman

Appendix B

List of adjectives with frequency in Tabular Form

Table 1. Adjectives occurring with man in TTP

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with man in TTP	Frequency
1	young man	13
2	old man	6
3	educated man	2
4	lean man	2
5	Big man	1
6	Brave man	1
7	Bravest man	1
8	Clever man	1
9	Great man	1
10	Greatest man	1
11	Lifeless man	1
12	married man	1
13	Religious man	1
14	Small man	1
15	Tallest man	1
16	Tired man	1
17	Violent man	1
18	wise man	1
19	Younger man	1

Table 2. Adjectives occurring with man in TTP with positive connotation

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with man in TTP	Frequency
1	young man	13
2	educated man	2
3	Big man	1
4	Brave man	1
5	Bravest man	1
6	Clever man	1
7	Great man	1
8	Greatest man	1
9	married man	1
10	Religious man	1
11	Tallest man	1
12	wise man	1
13	Younger man	1

Table 3. Adjectives occurring with man in TTP with negative connotation

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with man in TTP	Frequency
1	old man	6
2	lean man	2
3	Lifeless man	1
4	Small man	1
5	Tired man	1
6	Violent man	1

Table 4. Adjectives occurring with man in TICM

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with man in TICM	Frequency
1	Ice-candy man	6
2	Old man	4
3	Holy man	3
4	grown man	2
5	Aged man	1
6	Bad man	1
7	chubby man	1
8	dead man	1
9	dear man	1
10	Donkey man	1
11	Fair man	1
12	Good man	1
13	Horrid man	1
14	Large man	1
15	Looking man	1
16	Medicine man	1
17	Mountain man	1
18	Paunchy man	1
19	Poor man	1
20	Thin man	1
21	Gentle	1
22	Younger	1

Table 5. Adjectives occurring with man in TICM with positive connotation

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with man in TICM	Frequency
1	Ice candy man	6
2	Holy man	3
3	dear man	1
4	Fair man	1
5	Good man	1
6	Large man	1
7	Looking man	1
8	Medicine man	1
9	mountain man	1
10	Gentle man	1
11	younger man	1

Table 6. Adjectives occurring with man in TICM with negative connotation

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with man in TICM	Frequency
1	old man	4
2	Grown man	2
3	aged man	1
4	Bad man	1
5	Chubby man	1
6	dead man	1
7	Donkey man	1
8	Horrid man	1
9	Paunchy man	1
10	Poor man	1

11 | Thin man | 1

Table 7. Adjectives occurring with woman in TTP

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with woman in TTP	Frequency
1	Old woman	19
2	Abducted woman	1
3	older woman	1
4	strange woman	1
5	toothless woman	1

Table 8. Adjectives occurring with woman in TICM

Sr. No.	Adjectives occurring with woman in TICM	Frequency
1	Fallen woman	3
2	old woman	2
3	Aged woman	1
4	Flashy woman	1
5	Son-less woman	1
6	Poor woman	1
7	Rollicking woman	1
8	Poor fate-smitten woman	1
9	Sorrowing woman	1
10	Wailing woman	1